

THERAPEUTIC INSIGHTS INTO AJEYA GHRITA: A CRITICAL REVIEW OF ITS UNIVERSAL ANTI POISONOUS PROPERTIES IN AGADA TANTRA

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ABSTRACT

Agada Tantra, one of the eight classical branches of *Ayurveda*, focuses on the diagnosis and management of various forms of poisoning, including *Garavisha* (artificial poison) and *Dushi Visha* (attenuated or chronic poison). These poisons, often encountered in daily life through contaminated food, drugs, or cosmetics, disrupt the body's internal balance over time. Among the many *Agada* formulations prescribed for such conditions, *Ajeya Ghrita* - a medicated ghee formulation mentioned in *Ashtanga Sangraha* and *Sushruta Samhita*- stands out for its comprehensive detoxifying potential. Composed of 25 drugs, including potent *Vishaghna Dravyas* like *Haridra*, *Manjishta*, *Ela*, and *Chandana*, along with *Go-ghrita* as a bio-enhancing carrier, this formulation effectively penetrates and purifies deep tissues, balances *Doshas*, and eliminates toxins. This review highlights the *Sarvavisha Nashana* (universal anti-poisonous) properties of *Ajeya Ghrita*, underscoring its

therapeutic value in managing various toxicological conditions.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Agada tantra, Ajeya ghrita, Garavisha, Dushi visha, Kritrima visha.*

INTRODUCTION

Agada Tantra is a distinctive branch among the eight classical divisions of *Ayurveda*, specializing in the understanding, diagnosis, and treatment of various types of poisoning.^[1]

Within this system, *Garavisha* - An artificially created poison is described as a form of *Visha* (toxin). It results from the combination of two or more substances, which may be either toxic or non-toxic. Over time, this compound poison gradually accumulates in the body, disrupting the balance of *Doshas* (bodily humors), *Dhatus* (tissues), *Malas* (waste products), and *Srotas* (body channels).^[2]

Dushi visha - Poison which is old (stored for long) or attenuated by anti-poisonous remedies or dried in forest fire, wind and the sun or naturally deficient in properties attains the nature of '*dushi visha*' It is not fatal due to mild potency and being covered with *kapha*, it stays in body for a number of years.^[3]

Due to changing lifestyle people are exposed to one or other kind of poisons in their day to day life. This exposure is in the form of food, drinks, drugs, cosmetics etc. This concept can be well correlated with *Kritrima visha* explained in the classical texts of *Ayurveda*.

Kritrima visha is called as *Garavisha* according to *Vagbhatta*.^[4]

Several *Agada* formulations have been outlined for the treatment of *Garavisha* and *Dushi visha*, among which *Ajeya Ghrita* holds a significant place. Mentioned in the *Ashtanga Sangraha* and *Sushruta Samhita*, it belongs to the category of *Ghrita Kalpa* (medicated ghee preparations). *Ghrita* based formulation play an essential role in managing poisoning conditions due to their penetrative and nourishing properties. *Ajeya Ghrita* is a multi-drug formulation (that contains 25 drugs in it) with most of its ingredients known for their *Vishaghna* properties.

Vishaghna Dravyas like *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*), *Manjishta*(*Rubia cordifolia*), *Ela*(*Elattariacardamomum*) and *Chandana* (*Santalum album*) etc.

Go-ghrita (cow ghee), which acts as a *Yogavahi*-a carrier that enhances bioavailability and penetrates deep tissues.

The combination allows the formulation to act at both physical and subtle levels, removing toxins lodged in *Dhatus* (tissues) and balancing *Doshas*.

The formulation is simple to prepare and consists of easily available ingredients, making it a practical option for *Ayurvedic* practitioners. Therefore, this review aims to explore the *Sarvavisha Nashana* efficacy of *Ajeya Ghrita* and its relevance in the treatment of various toxic conditions.

DRUG REVIEW^[5]

मधुकं तगरं कुष्ठभद्रदारुहरेणवः |

मंजिष्ठैलैलवालूनि नागपुष्पोत्पलं प्लवम् ||

विडंगं चन्दनं पत्रंप्रियंगुधर्यामकं बला |

अंशुमत्यौ हरिद्रे द्वे ब्रहत्यौ सारिवाद्वयम् ||

एषां कल्कैघृतं सिद्धमजेयं नाम विश्रुतम् |

विषाणि हन्ति सर्वाणि शीघ्रमेव प्रयोजितम् || (Astanga-samgraha 40/130-132)

Table 1: Ingredients of Ajeya Ghrita.

Sr.no.	Dravya (Drug)	Rasa (Taste)	Guna (Properties)	Veerya (Potency)	Vipaka (Metabolic Property)
1	<i>Madhuka</i> ^[6] (<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (unctuous)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
2	<i>Tagara</i> ^[7] (<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
3	<i>Kushta</i> ^[8] (<i>Saussurea lappa</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
4	<i>Bhadradaru</i> ^[9] (<i>Cedrus deodara</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)

5	<i>Harenu</i> ^[10] (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
6	<i>Manjishta</i> ^[11] (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy), <i>Ruksha</i> (rough)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
7	<i>Ela</i> ^[12] (<i>Elattariacardamomum</i>)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
8	<i>Elavaluka</i> ^[13] (<i>Prunus cerasus</i>)	<i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
9	<i>Nagapushpa</i> ^[14] (<i>Mesua ferra</i>)	<i>Kashaya</i> (astringent) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Ruksha</i> (dry) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp) <i>Laghu</i> (light)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)/ <i>Anushna</i> (Not hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
10	<i>Utpala</i> ^[15] (<i>Nymphaea alba</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous) <i>Picchila</i> (sliminess)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
11	<i>Plava</i> ^[16] (<i>Cyperus scariosus</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
12	<i>Vidanga</i> ^[17] (<i>Embelia ribes Burm.</i>)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
13	<i>Chandana</i> ^[18] (<i>Santalum album Linn.</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
14	<i>Patra</i> ^[19] (<i>Abes webbiana</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
15	<i>Priyangu</i> ^[20] (<i>Callicarpa macrophylla Vahl</i>)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent) <i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
16	<i>Dhyamaka</i> ^[21] (<i>Cymbopogon martini</i>)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
17	<i>Bala</i> ^[22] (<i>Sida cardifolia Linn.</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Snighna</i> (unctuous) <i>Picchila</i> (sliminess)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
18	<i>Shalaparni</i> ^[23] (<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)

19	<i>Prushniparni</i> ^[24] (<i>Uraria picta</i> Desv.)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
20	<i>Haridra</i> ^[25] (<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn.)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Katu</i> (pungent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
21	<i>Daru haridra</i> ^[26] (<i>Berberis aristata</i> Dc.)	<i>Tikta</i> (bitter) <i>Kashaya</i> (astringent)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
22	<i>Bruhati</i> ^[27] (<i>Solanum indicum</i> Linn.)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
23	<i>Kantakari</i> ^[28] (<i>Solanum</i> <i>xanthocarpum</i> Schrad.)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Ruksha</i> (dry) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp)	<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Katu</i> (pungent)
24	<i>Shwetha Sariva</i> ^[29] (<i>Hemodisum indicus</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)
25	<i>Krishna Sariva</i> ^[29] (<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i> <i>R. Br.</i>)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet) <i>Tikta</i> (bitter)	<i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (Unctuous)	<i>Sheeta</i> (cold)	<i>Madhura</i> (sweet)

Table 2: Action & Indications.

Sl. No	<i>Dravya</i> (Drug)	<i>Doshagnata</i> (action on <i>dosha</i>)	<i>Karma</i> (action)	<i>Rogagnata</i> (therapeutic indications)
1	<i>Madhuka</i> ^[6] (<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>)	<i>VataPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Vata</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Balya</i> (strengthens the body) <i>Shukrala</i> (increases seminal flow)	<i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst) <i>Kshaya</i> (cachexia)
2	<i>Tagara</i> ^[7] (<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Vishaghna</i> (anti poisonous)	<i>Anidra</i> (insomnia) <i>Apasmara</i> (epilepsy)
3	<i>Kushta</i> ^[8] (<i>Saussurea lappa</i>)	<i>VataKaphahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> and <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Lekhaniya</i> (scraping) <i>Vrishya</i> (aphrodisiac) <i>Vishaghna</i> (anti poisonous)	<i>Kushta</i> (leprosy) <i>Hikka</i> (hiccups) <i>Kasa</i> (cough) <i>Swasa</i> (difficulty in breathing) <i>Hridroga</i> (cardiac diseases) <i>Kandu</i> (itching) <i>Visarpa</i> (erysipelas)
4	<i>Bhadradaru</i> ^[9] (<i>Cedrus deodara</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Deepana</i> (gastrostimulant)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>DushtaVrana</i> (non- healing ulcer) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Krimi</i> (worm infestation)

5	<i>Harenu</i> ^[10] (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Grahi</i> (one which holds)	<i>Dahapaha</i> (relieves burning sensation) <i>Pushtiprada</i> (improves strength)
6	<i>Manjishtha</i> ^[11] (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Varnya Vishaghna</i> (anti poisonous)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Visarpa</i> (Herpes)
7	<i>Ela</i> ^[12] (<i>Elattariacardamo mum</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Hridya</i> (cardioprotective) <i>Deepana</i> (gastrostimulant)	<i>Hidroga</i> (cardiac disease) <i>Swasa</i> (difficulty in breathing) <i>Kasa</i> (cough) <i>Mutrakrichra</i> (dysuria) <i>Chardi</i> (emesis) <i>Arshas</i> (piles)
8	<i>Elavaluka</i> ^[13] (<i>Prunus cerasus</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Shukra shodhana</i> (semen purifier)	<i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Vrana</i> (wound) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Murcha</i> (unconsciousness) <i>Hridruja</i> (cardiac disease)
9	<i>Nagapushpa</i> ^[14] (<i>Mesua ferra</i>)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Vishahara</i> (anti poisonous) <i>Kushtaghna</i> (alleviates skin disease) <i>Shothahara</i> (alleviated inflammation)	<i>Visha roga</i> (poisoning conditions) <i>Kushta</i> (skin diseases) <i>Visarpa</i> (herpes) <i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst)
10	<i>Utpala</i> ^[15] (<i>Nymphaea alba</i>)	<i>Tridoshahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Medhya</i> (improves intellect) <i>Mutra virajana</i> (restoring normal urine color) <i>Grahi</i> (one which holds)	<i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst) <i>Daha</i> (burning sensation) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Jwara</i> (Fever) <i>Atisara</i> (diarrhea)
11	<i>Plava</i> ^[16] (<i>Cyperus scariosus</i>)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Deepana</i> (gastro stimulant) <i>Pachana Grahi</i> (one which holds) <i>Lekhana</i> (scraping)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Apasmara</i> (epilepsy) <i>Grahani</i> (ulcerative colitis) <i>Nidranasha</i> (insomnia) <i>Raktavikara</i> (disorders of blood)
12	<i>Vidanga</i> ^[17] (<i>Embelia ribes Burm.</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Vishaghna</i> (antipoisonous) <i>Krimighna</i> (anthelmintic) <i>Deepana</i> (gastro stimulant)	<i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Udara</i> (ascites) <i>Adhmana</i> (bloating) <i>Krimi</i> (worm infestation) <i>Shoola</i> (pain)

13	<i>Chandana</i> ^[18] (<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Varnya</i> (skin whitening) <i>Dahaprashamana</i> (alleviates burning sensation)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst) <i>Daha</i> (burning sensation) <i>Visarpa</i> (herpes)
14	<i>Patra</i> ^[19] (<i>Abes webbiana</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Hridya</i> (cardioprotective) <i>Deepana</i> (gastro stimulant)	<i>Aruchi</i> (anorexia) <i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder) <i>Kshaya</i> (cachexia) <i>Shwasa</i> (dyspnea)
15	<i>Priyangu</i> ^[20] (<i>Callicarpa</i> <i>macrophylla</i> Vahl)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Mutra virajana</i> (restoring normal urine color) <i>Purishasangrahaniya</i> (bowel binding)	<i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst) <i>Daha</i> (burning sensation) <i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes)
16	<i>Dhyamaka</i> ^[21] (<i>Cymbopogon</i> <i>martini</i>)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Sthanya janana</i> (Galactogogues)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Daha</i> (burning sensation) <i>Trishna</i> (excessive thirst) <i>Chardi</i> (emesis) <i>Kasa</i> (cough) <i>Swasa</i> (difficulty in breathing) <i>Krimi</i> (microbial disorder) <i>Arshas</i> (piles)
17	<i>Bala</i> ^[22] (<i>Sida cardifolia</i> Linn.)	<i>KaphaPittahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i>)	<i>Balya</i> (strength promoter) <i>Brumhana</i> (nourishment) <i>Vrushya</i> (aphrodisiac)	<i>Vatavyadhi</i> (diseases of <i>Vata</i>) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Kshaya</i> (cachexia) <i>RaktaPitta</i> (bleeding disorder)
18	<i>Shalaparni</i> ^[23] (<i>Desmodium</i> <i>gangeticum</i>)	<i>Tridoshahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Balya</i> (strength promoter) <i>Vrushya</i> (aphrodisiac)	<i>Jwara</i> (Fever) <i>Atisara</i> (diarrhea) <i>Krimi</i> (worm infestation) <i>Shota</i> (inflammation) <i>Chardi</i> (vomiting)
19	<i>Prushniparni</i> ^[24] (<i>Uraria picta</i> Desv.)	<i>Tridoshahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Vrushya</i> (aphrodisiac) <i>Deepana</i> (gastro stimulant) <i>Grahi</i> (which holds)	<i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Daha</i> (burning sensation) <i>Trishna</i> (thirst) <i>Chardi</i> (Vomiting) <i>Shwasa</i> (dyspnea)
20	<i>Haridra</i> ^[25] (<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn.)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Vishaghana</i> (anti poisonous) <i>Lekhana</i> (scraping) <i>Varnya</i> (enhances complexion)	<i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Krimi</i> (worm infestation) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Pandu</i> (anemia) <i>Kamala</i> (jaundice)

21	<i>Daru haridra</i> ^[26] (<i>Berberis aristata</i> Dc.)	<i>Kaphahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Madakari</i> (intoxicating) <i>Grahi</i> (binding) <i>Shukrasthambhaka</i> (preventing early ejaculation)	<i>Nidra Nasha</i> (insomnia) <i>Klaibya</i> (impotency) <i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Atisara</i> (diarrhea) <i>Kasa</i> (cough)
22	<i>Bruhati</i> ^[27] (<i>Solanum indicum</i> Linn.)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Shukra rechaka</i> (assist easy ejaculation of sperm)	<i>Hrudroga</i> (cardiac ailments) <i>Kushta</i> (skin disease) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Krimi</i> (worm infestation) <i>Shwasa</i> (dyspnea) <i>Jwara</i> (fever)
23	<i>Kantakari</i> ^[28] (<i>Solanum</i> <i>xanthocarpum</i> Schrad.)	<i>KaphaVatahara</i> (Alleviates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>)	<i>Deepana</i> (gastro-stimulant) <i>Pachana</i> (digestive) <i>Ashmarighna</i> (lithotriptic) <i>Mutrala</i> (diuretic) <i>Shukrarchaka</i> (assist easy ejaculation of sperm)	<i>Ashmari</i> (calculi) <i>Mutrakricchra</i> (dysuria) <i>Shota</i> (inflammation) <i>Shwasa</i> (dyspnea) <i>Kasa</i> (cough)
24	<i>Shwetha Sariva</i> ^[29] (<i>Hemidismus</i> <i>indicus</i>)	<i>Tridoshahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Grahi</i> (binding)	<i>Aruchi</i> (anorexia) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Atisara</i> (diarrhea)
25	<i>Krishna Sariva</i> ^[29] (<i>Ichnocarpus</i> <i>frutescens</i> R. Br.)	<i>Tridoshahara</i> (alleviates <i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>)	<i>Grahi</i> (binding)	<i>Aruchi</i> (anorexia) <i>Prameha</i> (diabetes) <i>Kandu</i> (pruritis) <i>Jwara</i> (fever) <i>Atisara</i> (diarrhea)

METHOD OF PREPARATION^[30]

Equal quantities of each of the drugs are powdered separately, mixed and made into the form of a paste. This is to be added to 4 parts of *Ghrita* (ghee) and 16 parts of water. It has to be cooked on medium heat till the water portion gets evaporated and *Ghrita* (ghee) becomes free from froth. Then it is filtered and stored in an airtight container.

INDICATION^[31]

Sthavara visha (plant poison), *Jangama visha* (animal poison), *Kritrima visha* (artificial poison) and all types of *Visha* (poison) conditions.

PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION

Based on *Veerya* (potency) of ingredients

56% of the ingredients are having *Ushna* (hot) *Veerya* and 44% of the ingredients are having *Sheeta* (cold) *Veerya*.

Based on the *Doshagnata* (action on *dosha*) of ingredients

The majority of the ingredients of this formulation is having *Kapha-Vatahara* (alleviates *Kapha* and *Vata*) and also having *Tridosahara* (alleviates *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*) property.

DISCUSSION

Ajeya Ghrita is recommended for use in various forms of poisoning (*Visha*). This medicinal preparation consists of 25 drugs, among which 14 possess *Ushna Veerya* (hot potency) and 11 exhibit *Sheeta Veerya* (cold potency). The majority of these drugs have *Laghu Guna* (lightness), which facilitates quicker action, while the *Snigdha Guna* (unctuous quality) of the ingredients aids in neutralizing toxins. Most of the components are known to pacify *Kapha* and *Vata doshas* (*Kapha-vatahara*) and also balance all three *doshas* (*Tridosahara*), thereby helping to mitigate the harmful effects of toxins in the body.

The ingredients in *Ajeya Ghrita* are known for their *Vishaghna* (anti-toxic) properties. It has also been demonstrated to offer protection to the heart (*Hrudayavarana*), primarily by enhancing antioxidant mechanisms like catalase activity and by reducing lipid peroxidation in the membranes of myocardial cells. These effects help in preventing cellular damage caused by free radicals.^[32]

Ghrita (ghee), which serves as the base of this formulation, naturally possesses *Tridosahara* and *Vishaghna* properties.^[33]

It is widely used as a primary ingredient or as an *Anupana* (vehicle) in formulations aimed at neutralizing toxins. Ghee is rich in vitamins A and E, which assist in decreasing ketone body formation. Additionally, it contains beta-carotene, a potent antioxidant, further contributing to its protective effects.^[34]

CONCLUSION

When poison (*Visha*) enters the body, it primarily targets the heart (*Hridaya*) and endangers the individual's life. The use of *Ghrita* (medicated ghee) helps in counteracting the toxic effects and safeguards the heart. Therefore, *Ghrita Kalpa* (ghee-based formulations) play an important role in managing poisoning.

Ajeya Ghrita stands out as a potent remedy due to its unique combination of *Vishaghna Dravyas* and the carrier property of *Go-ghrita*. Its ability to penetrate deep tissues, neutralize toxins, and restore *doshic* balance highlights its efficacy in managing toxic conditions.

Simple in preparation and composed of readily available drugs, *Ajeya Ghrita* offers a practical and effective approach for *Ayurvedic* practitioners in the treatment of all forms of *Visha*, reinforcing its significance in the field of *Agada Tantra*.

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